

RADIOLOGIC PATHOLOGIC RELATIONSHIP AMONG THE TUMOR DEPTH OF INVASION ORAL SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA OF TONGUE

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Abstract

Objective: "To assess the correlation between the radiological and pathological findings in the measurement of tumor depth of invasion oral squamous cell carcinoma of tongue"

Study Design: Correlational study

Setting and duration: Department of Oncology, University of Lahore, Lahore from Jan 2024 to June 2024

Methodology: After meeting the selection criteria, 32 patients were enrolled. Informed consent was obtained, and demographic details were recorded. Patients aged 18 to 80 years of both genders, diagnosed with oral squamous cell carcinoma of the tongue, and consenting to both radiological and pathological examinations were included. The depth of invasion (DOI) from both examinations was measured according to the operational definitions. All data were documented on the pre-designed proforma attached below.

Results: The patients had a mean age of 46.56 ± 6.37 years and a mean BMI of 18.74 ± 0.85 kg/m². Comorbidity assessment showed that 10 (31.3%) were diabetic, 19 (59.4%) were hypertensive, and 22 (68.8%) were smokers. This study demonstrated a strong positive correlation between radiological and pathological findings for tumor depth of invasion ($r = 0.900$, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: It can be concluded that there is a strong correlation that is positive between radiological and pathological findings in measuring the tumor depth of invasion in oral squamous cell carcinoma of the tongue.

INTRODUCTION

Oral cancers are highly aggressive due to their ability to spread to nearby lymph nodes, leading

to a poorer prognosis¹. Squamous cell carcinoma of the tongue (TSCC) is one of the more

aggressive forms of oral cancer that has a high recurrence rate². OSCC, or oral squamous cell carcinoma, the sixth most common kind of cancer globally, most frequently affects the front two-thirds of the tongue³.

Globally the prevalence of cancers of the Oral Cavity is 350,000 cases, with a ratio of 2.1:1 in males and females respectively⁴. About 500,000 newly instances of “head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC)” are detected each year, with a rise in “oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC)”⁵. Annual global mortality rate among OSCC patients is 145,000 where alcohol and tobacco usage stand out as the primary risk factors. This is heightened in Southern Asian countries due to the widespread use of chewing tobacco, which is frequently coupled with betel quid use⁵. In Pakistan, OSCC is reported to be the most prevalent cancer in males⁶. With a poor 5 year survival rate, the prognosis for OSCC remains poor despite improvements in diagnosis and therapy⁷.

Verifying the accuracy of a parameter's radiologic vs pathologic measurement and its prognostic relevance is necessary to ensure the practical use of the 8th edition clinical T-classification for OSCC⁸. Accurate diagnosis and staging of tongue cancer help to select an appropriate therapeutic approach, including tumor excision and removal of cervical lymph nodes if necessary. A histological metric called depth of the invasion (DOI) gauges distance between the basement membrane and the deepest point of tumor tissue in the underlying structure⁹.

Traditionally histopathological examination including surgical specimen were used to determine the DOI, however various methods have been used to determine DOI preoperatively using ultrasound, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computed tomography (CT); MRI is the preferred test for assessing tongue tumors. It provides essential information on tumor location, dimensions, infiltration, and DOI; however, the accuracy and predictive value of MRI-measured DOI are variable and have not been validated. This study aimed to assess correlation between radiological and pathological data in order to

ascertain the tumor depth of invasion of oral squamous cell carcinoma of the tongue.

METHODOLOGY

After taking ethical approval from institutional review board, this correlational study was carried out at department of Oncology, University of Lahore, Lahore from (from Jan 2024 to June 2024).

The calculated sample size for this study was 10 sample using pooled correlation coefficient between radiologic depth of invasion and pathologic depth of invasion in oral cavity squamous cell carcinoma as 0.86.¹⁰ For this study calculation the level of significance was 5% and power of study was 90%. For getting better results we enlarge the sample size and rounded off it to 32 patients. All the patients were enrolled by applying non-probability convenient sampling technique.

Inclusion: The patients having age range between 18 to 80 years of both genders presented with oral squamous cell carcinoma of tongue and agreed for radiological and pathological examination were fall in inclusion criteria.

Exclusion: Patients on prior treatment or on chemo or radiotherapy, patients presented with recurrent tumor and patients with unclear mucosal reference for pathological DOI were fall in exclusion criteria.

On initial evaluation, demographic information and co-morbid condition were noted in all the patients. After that patients were evaluated for radiological and pathological examination by expert radiologist and pathologist. Radiological findings were measured by calculating the perpendicular distance between the mucosal surface and deepest point of tumor on the basis of MRI and CT scan by expert radiologist applying standard imaging protocols. The measurement of perpendicular distance and deepest point of tumor calculated by histopathology examination on the basis of surgical examination was labeled as pathological findings. The strength of relationship between two modalities reporting on DOI was calculated

by applying correlation analysis. All the data was collected on pre-designed Proforma.

All the collected data was entered and analyzed on SPSS version 26. All the quantitative data like, age, BMI, tumor size, tumor thickness and depth of invasion, were presented in the form of mean \pm SD. All the qualitative data like gender, residence, co-morbid conditions were presented in the form of frequency and percentage. To know the relationship between radiologic and pathologic findings Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated while $p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$ was taken as significant.

RESULTS

In this study, a total of 32 cases were enrolled. The Mean age was 46.56 ± 6.37 years, and the Mean BMI was 18.74 ± 0.85 kg/m². Of these, 21 (65.6%) were male. The most common occupation was laborer, observed in 50% of cases, followed by housewives, drivers, and construction

workers. Regarding socioeconomic status, 25 (78.1%) cases belonged to the low socioeconomic status group, while 7 (21.9%) were from middle class. Comorbidity analysis revealed that 10 (31.3%) patients were diabetic, 19 (59.4%) were hypertensive and 22 (68.8%) were smokers. Alcohol consumption and tobacco use were reported in 3 (9.4%) and 22 (68.8%) cases, respectively. A family history of cancer was present in 4 (12.5%) cases. In terms of cancer staging, T2 tumors were observed in 3 (9.4%) cases, whereas T3 tumors were seen in 29 (90.6%) cases. The mean pathological tumor thickness was 8.95 ± 1.23 cm, compared to a mean radiological tumor thickness of 10.71 ± 1.37 cm. The mean depth of invasion was 6.61 ± 1.40 cm based on pathological findings and 8.57 ± 1.72 cm based on radiological findings. **Table-I**

Table-I: Basic socio-demographic, clinical, radiological and pathological parameters of patients (n = 32)

Parameters		Output
Age (Years)		46.56 \pm 6.37
Gender	Male	21 (65.6%)
	Female	11 (34.4%)
BMI (Kg/m ²)		18.74 \pm 0.85
Occupation	Car washer	1 (3.1%)
	Constructor	2 (6.3%)
	Driver	3 (9.4%)
	Farmer	1 (3.1%)
	Housewife	5 (15.6%)
	Labour	16 (50.0%)
	Painter	1 (3.1%)
	Shopkeeper	1 (3.1%)
	Sweeper	2 (6.3%)
Duration of symptoms (months)		7.94 \pm 3.59
Socioeconomic status	Low	25 (78.1%)
	Middle	7 (21.9%)
	High	0 (0.0%)
Diabetes	Yes	10 (31.3%)
	No	22 (68.8%)
Hypertension	Yes	13 (40.6%)
	No	19 (59.4%)
Smoking	Yes	22 (68.8%)
	No	10 (31.3%)

Tobacco Use	Yes	22 (68.8%)
	No	10 (31.3%)
Family history of cancer	Yes	4 (12.5%)
	No	28 (87.5%)
Use of alcohol	Yes	3 (9.4%)
	No	29 (90.6%)
Cancer staging	T2	3 (9.4%)
	T3	29 (90.6%)
pT category	No	10 (31.3%)
	PN+	22 (68.8%)
pN category	No	4 (12.5%)
	PN+	28 (87.5%)
Pathological Tumor Thickness (cm)		8.95 ± 1.23
Radiological Tumor Thickness (cm)		10.71 ± 1.37
Pathological depth of invasion (cm)		6.61 ± 1.40
Radiological depth of invasion (cm)		8.57 ± 1.72

Based on this study, a strong correlation that is positive was observed between the radiological and pathological findings for tumor depth of invasion ($r = 0.900$, $p < 0.001$). **Figure-1**

Figure-1: Correlation between radiological and pathological depth of invasion

Findings of this study demonstrated a strong correlation that is positive ($r \geq 0.5$) between radiological and pathological depth of invasion, when stratified by age, gender, socioeconomic

status, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, smoking status, tobacco and alcohol use, and family history of cancer. **Table-II**

Table-II: Correlation between radiological and pathological depth of invasion stratified by demographic and clinical parameters

		Pathological	Radiological
Age Groups	≤ 45 (n=15)	Pearson Correlation	0.892
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
	>45 (n=17)	Pearson Correlation	0.895

		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
Gender	Male (n=21)	Pearson Correlation	0.910
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
	Female (n=11)	Pearson Correlation	0.930
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
SES	Middle (n=25)	Pearson Correlation	0.868
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
	High (n=07)	Pearson Correlation	0.962
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
Diabetes Mellitus	Yes (n=10)	Pearson Correlation	0.716
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.020
	No (n=22)	Pearson Correlation	0.943
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
Hypertension	Yes (n=13)	Pearson Correlation	0.859
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
	No (n=19)	Pearson Correlation	0.924
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
Smoking	Yes (n=22)	Pearson Correlation	0.890
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
	No (n=10)	Pearson Correlation	0.941
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
Tobacco	Yes (n=22)	Pearson Correlation	0.918
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
	No (n=10)	Pearson Correlation	0.836
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
FH of cancer	Yes (n=04)	Pearson Correlation	0.994
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.006
	No (n=28)	Pearson Correlation	0.895
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000

DISCUSSION:

Squamous Cell Carcinoma of the Oral Cavity, Eighth most prevalent kind of cancer globally, mostly affects the front two thirds of the tongue^{11, 12}. Because Oral Tongue Squamous Cell carcinoma (OTSCC) lacks a robust barrier to stop tumor growth and has a well-developed lymphovascular system, its prognosis is generally poor¹³. The prognosis of oral cavity squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) is directly correlated with the depth of infiltration of a tumor^{14, 15}.

Similar to our study findings Lee et al., According to the data, the MD and pooled correlation coefficient were 1.84 mm (95 % CI, 1.02-2.65 mm; I2 = 88.2 %) and 0.86 (95 % CI, 0.82-0.90; I2 = 66.7 %), respectively. MRI had the greatest

MD (n = 12, 2.61 mm) in the subgroup analysis, followed by CT (n = 2, 0.12 mm) and US (n = 2, -0.41 mm). The correlation coefficient was greatest for the US (n = 3, 0.91), followed by CT (n = 3, 0.82) and MRI (n = 12, 0.85)¹⁰. One more study by E.A.M. In 354 consecutive patients, Weimar et al. found that the radiologic-pathologic tumor thickness association was lower in patients with an interval of more than 8 weeks ($\rho = 0.62$), but similar for those with an image-to-surgery gap of ≤ 4.0 weeks ($\rho = 0.76$) versus 4-8 weeks ($\rho = 0.80$). Correlations between CT and MR imaging were comparable (0.76 and 0.80). The reliability of the interrater and intratester was excellent (0.88 and 0.84)⁸.

Tang et al., found that the best association between pathogenic DOI and DOI obtained by e-THRIVE ($r = 0.936$, $p < 0.001$). The MRI-derived DOI's area under the curve values for differentiating between the T1 and T2 stages and between the T2 and T3 stages were 0.969 and 0.974, respectively. In contrast to the pathological DOI criteria of 5 mm and 10 mm, the T staging criteria of MRI-derived DOI were 6.2 mm and 11.4 mm, with a staging accuracy of 86.9%¹⁶.

While correlations are intriguing, one aspect that needs further focus is that the overestimation of T stages was caused by the MRI-derived DOI being much bigger than the histopathological DOI^{17, 18}. Furthermore, there was disagreement on the precise discrepancy, which was up to 3.5 mm¹⁹. Baba et al²⁰ discovered that histopathological DOI and CE-T1WI-derived DOI were more strongly correlated, and that CE-T1WI-derived DOI was somewhat more accurate to quantify than T2WI-derived DOI. Another viewpoint was that each patient had a different ideal MR sequence^{21, 22}.

It is suggested that future research be conducted to further validate the findings of our study. Due to time and financial constraints, our sample size was limited. Therefore, it is recommended that future studies can come along with larger sample sizes and data collected from multiple centers, enabling the results to be generalized to the wider population.

CONCLUSION:

On the basis of this study, we may conclude that there is strong correlation that is positive between the radiological and pathological findings in the measurement of tumor depth of invasion oral squamous cell carcinoma of tongue.

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